

The effect of body mass index on pressure controlled ventilator settings

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Abstract: In this article, we present an approach to determine the most indulgent inspiratory pressure and inspiratory time for pressure controlled ventilation as a function of BMI for a patient with healthy lungs. The lung mechanics are strongly influenced by obesity as airway resistance increases and the lung compliance decreases with increasing BMI. Based on a linear single compartment model of the lung and parameter values depending on the BMI, a ventilator setting minimizing inspiration pressure P_I for a given minute volume can be determined. First a constant PEEP of 10 cmH₂O is assumed. The results of the optimization show that an increased inspiratory pressure P_I as well as a slightly increased inspiratory time t_I are necessary to achieve a given minute volume with increasing BMI. In the second step, a BMI-dependent PEEP is added, illustrating different effects of the BMI. The proposed approach is a first step to ensure efficient and safe, patient-individualized mechanical ventilation for obese patients.

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I. Introduction

Overweight, measured e.g. with the body mass index (BMI , [kg/m^2]), has a strong influence on the patient's lung mechanics. Due to the additional pressure on the thorax and abdomen through the extra fat deposits, the breathing resistance R increases and the compliance of the lung C decreases [1]. As a result, tidal volume V_T and functional residual capacity FRC decrease [2]. All these changes occurring for obese patients should be considered for a proper choice of ventilation parameters in pressure controlled ventilation to achieve the most indulgent, patient-individualized mechanical ventilation. In this work, the goal is to find a set of parameters based on clinical data that protects the patient's lungs. This is achieved by choosing the smallest but still safe value for the inspiration pressure while still ensuring an adequate minute volume.

In [3], Pelosi et al. established a relationship between BMI to airway resistance R and lung compliance C in a clinical study of 24 volume-controlled ventilated patients and described it as follows [3]:

$$R(BMI) = 2.55 \cdot e^{0.03 \cdot BMI} \left[\frac{\text{cmH}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{s}}{\text{L}} \right]. \quad (1)$$

$$C(BMI) = 233.3 \cdot e^{-0.086 \cdot BMI} + 40 \left[\frac{\text{mL}}{\text{cmH}_2\text{O}} \right]. \quad (2)$$

Additionally, the influence of positive end-expiratory pressure ($PEEP$, cmH₂O) should be considered. To prevent collapse from the alveoli during expiration, increased $PEEP$ is advisable in obese patients. Reindl et al. [4] suggested on the basis of a study with 91 patients:

$$PEEP(BMI) = \frac{BMI}{4} [\text{cmH}_2\text{O}]. \quad (3)$$

II. Material and methods

We exemplarily consider a man of 1.8 m height with a weight ranging from 70 to 160 kg for description of our methods. This corresponds to a BMI of 21.6 to 49.3 kg/m².

To determine the ideal tidal volume, the widely used rule of thumb $V_{T_{ideal}} = IBW \cdot 6$ to $8 \frac{\text{mL}}{\text{kg IBW}}$ (here: ideal body weight: $IBW = 75$ kg, resulting in $V_{T_{ideal}}$ of 450 to 800 mL) is used [5]. Based on this, the tidal volume of $V_{T_{ideal}} = 500$ mL has been chosen. Using this ideal tidal volume $V_{T_{ideal}}$, the minute volume is computed. A breath duration of $t_A = 5$ s is assumed. Based on these assumptions the minute volume \dot{V}_A is determined:

$$\dot{V}_A = V_{T_{ideal}} \left(\frac{60}{t_A} \right) = 6 \frac{\text{L}}{\text{min}}. \quad (4)$$

Note, that the estimated minute volume \dot{V}_A is independent of the BMI and the inspiration time t_I and chose merely for illustrations purposes. In an automated system, the minute volume could e.g. be computed by a higher level etCO₂ controller, see e.g. [6]. The dead space volume is necessary for further computation. This can also be estimated from the IBW [7]:

$$V_D = 2 \frac{\text{mL}}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{IBW}} = 0.15 \text{ L}, \quad (5)$$

or derived from blood gas measurements. Subsequently, the tidal volume V_T may be determined as a function of the inspiratory time $t_I = (0 - 4)$ s and the expiratory time $t_E = 3 \cdot \tau_E$ with $\tau_E = C(BMI) \cdot R(BMI)$. It results [7]:

$$V_T = \dot{V}_A (t_I + t_E) + V_D. \quad (8)$$

Next, the wanted inspiratory pressure P_I is computed [5]:

$$P_I = \frac{RC^2 \left(e^{\frac{t_R}{RC}} - 1 \right) PEEP - t_R e^{\frac{t_I}{RC}} (C \cdot PEEP + V_T)}{C \left[RC \left(e^{\frac{t_R}{RC}} - 1 \right) - t_R e^{\frac{t_I}{RC}} \right]}, \quad (9)$$

under the assumption of a linear first order model. Finally, the minimum of the resulting curves is resolved to determine the smallest value for the inspiration pressure P_I .

III. Results and discussion

In this approach, the minute volume \dot{V}_A has been fixed via the $V_{T,ideal}$. Based on this, a variable $V_T(t_I)$ is determined as shown in Eq. (8). In the first step, a constant $PEEP = 10 \text{ cmH}_2\text{O}$ is selected. For the exemplarily chosen subject, Fig. 1 it can be seen that the smallest inspiratory pressure P_I increases with increasing BMI .

Figure 1: Illustration of inspiration pressure P_I versus inspiratory time t_I with increasing BMI from 21.6 to 49.3 kg/m^2 and a constant $PEEP = 10 \text{ cmH}_2\text{O}$. * marks the minimum per BMI with the optimal inspiratory pressure P_I and time t_I .

In the second step, the $PEEP$ is increased with the BMI , as suggested in Eq. (3). The influence of the increasing $PEEP$ with BMI is shown in Fig. 2. On the one hand the $PEEP$ generates an offset such that the smallest inspiratory pressure P_I increases sharply compared to Fig. 1. On the other hand, the inspiratory time is obviously not affected by the adjustment of the $PEEP$. For detailed comparison see Tab. 1.

Figure 2: Illustration of inspiration pressure P_I versus inspiratory time t_I with increasing BMI from 21.6 to 49.3 kg/m^2 and a BMI dependent $PEEP = BMI/4 \text{ cmH}_2\text{O}$.

Table 1: Comparison of the results for the computation of the optimal inspiratory pressure P_I and the corresponding inspiratory time t_I with a constant $PEEP = 10 \text{ cmH}_2\text{O}$ and a variable $PEEP = BMI/4 \text{ cmH}_2\text{O}$.

BMI [kg/m^2]	PEEP = 10 cmH_2O		PEEP = BMI/4 cmH_2O	
	P_I [cmH_2O]	t_I [s]	P_I [cmH_2O]	t_I [s]
21.6	14.96	0.766	10.36	0.766
24.6	15.50	0.748	11.68	0.748
27.7	16.06	0.743	13.00	0.743
30.8	16.62	0.748	14.34	0.748
33.3	17.20	0.764	15.69	0.764
37.0	17.78	0.789	17.04	0.789
40.1	18.38	0.824	18.41	0.824
43.2	18.99	0.867	19.79	0.867
46.2	19.63	0.919	21.20	0.919
49.3	20.29	0.979	22.64	0.979

IV. Conclusions

In this article, a concept for finding the most indulgent parameter settings for mechanical ventilation in patients with obesity was presented. First simulations of the proposed approach show that changes in resistance R and lung compliance C due to obesity influence the ideal parameter settings of the ventilator as expected. For patients with obesity higher inspiration pressure P_I is needed to inflate the stiffened lungs. It was shown that the ideal inspiratory pressure P_I and the inspiratory time t_I increase with an increasing BMI . Because of the complexity of changes due to overweight in the lungs, it is not trivial to correctly adjust the ventilator and to avoid ventilator induced lung injuries. Therefore, this work is a first approach to assist the intensivist or anesthesiologist in setting initial ventilator parameters. Our future work will focus on substantiating this approach as well as extend towards patients body shape and pose.

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